
Skills development for managing longitudinal data for sharing

An evaluation and impact report on a project to enhance expertise within the Longitudinal Population Studies data managers community

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Executive Summary

This project was funded to enhance skills and expertise in managing and sharing Longitudinal Population Studies (LPS) data. The project's focus was on developing and delivering comprehensive training to data managers and researchers within the LPS community. The team conducted thorough audits of existing training resources, identified critical gaps in current training provision, and created new, targeted training materials.

To support the development of these materials, the team engaged with the LPS data management community through a survey, key stakeholder workshops, and follow up unstructured interviews with data managers, between September 2023 and January 2024, adopting a co-design approach. Additionally, a pilot training session was held to further refine and improve the training content based on direct feedback from LPS data managers.

Key deliverables included a series of specialised workshops and comprehensive training materials. The project successfully achieved its objectives by delivering effective training, gathering and incorporating participant feedback, and adapting its approach to meet the evolving needs of the LPS community, with particular emphasis on enhancing data management and sharing practices.

Next steps include three key areas of focus. Resources need to be hosted and directly discoverable on the PRUK hub. Expansion opportunities include presenting the materials at conferences, potential journal publications, and developing new partnerships. Stakeholder feedback suggests benefits in strengthening training materials in areas such as data linkage, metadata management, and data cleaning processes.

1. Scope

a. Funding

Materials were created under the [Skills Development for Managing Longitudinal Data for Sharing](#) project, funded by the [Economic and Social Research Council](#) (ESRC) and the [Medical Research Council](#) (MRC), part of an initial [Population Research UK](#) (PRUK) project.

b. Aims of the project

The project was established with several interconnected objectives focused on enhancing data management capabilities within the LPS community. Its primary aim was to expand the skills and expertise available to support wider sharing and increased utilisation of LPS data resources.

The project sought to provide comprehensive training and support to social science data producers and owners, enabling them to better understand and address challenges and barriers in data sharing.

A key focus was equipping participants and the wider longitudinal data community with standardised data management procedures to facilitate broader data sharing. The project also aimed to enhance researchers' skills in critical areas such as data formatting, documentation preparation, metadata management, and data anonymisation. It also focused on improving the efficiency and accuracy of longitudinal data analysis through enhanced data management processes.

c. Timeline

The project spanned 18 months from September 2023 to March 2025.

- September 2023: internal training materials audit
- October to December 2023: comprehensive audit of external training provision and needs assessment
- December 2023 and January 2024: focus on enhancing existing training provision
- January to April 2024: co-design of additional training materials
- April to November 2024: delivery phase, including training implementation and feedback collection ([see Appendix 1](#) for further details)
- November 2024 to March 2025: evaluation phase

d. Partners involved

Key partners included the broader Longitudinal Population Studies community, [Population Research UK](#) (PRUK), and the funding bodies the [Economic and Social Research Council](#) (ESRC) and MRC.

The collaboration extended to [CLOSER](#) and various prestigious academic institutions, including the [Institute for Social and Economic Research](#) (ISER) the [UCL Centre for Longitudinal Studies](#) (CLS), [UCL](#), the [University of Southampton](#), the [National Centre for Social Research](#) (NatCen), [Scottish Centre for Social Research](#) (ScotCen), the [University of Bristol](#), and [Queen's University Belfast](#).

Additional partners included the [National Centre for Research Methods](#) (NCRM), [Jisc](#), and specific studies such as [Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children](#) (ALSPAC), [Born in Bradford](#), and [Understanding Society – the UK Household Longitudinal Study](#).

2. Assessment of existing needs

a. Disciplinary differences

The project initially believed there to be significant differentiation in training needs between social science and biomedical studies. Historically, biomedical studies have placed less emphasis on data sharing compared to social sciences. It was initially considered that many existing training materials which had been predominantly tailored to social science data, would need substantial adaptation for biomedical contexts.

However, the survey with LPS data managers and the stakeholder workshop revealed the differences to be minimal across disciplines. Key training needs such as data linkage, metadata and documentation, file management, and data cleaning were consistently prioritised regardless of disciplinary background.

Despite operational differences, the core training needs, especially around standardisation, documentation, and data handling workflows, were remarkably consistent. This convergence suggested an opportunity to develop shared training resources that address common challenges, with modular elements that can be adapted to suit the specific contexts of either discipline.

b. Data types and formats

The assessment revealed considerable variation in the types and formats of data used across longitudinal studies, resulting in diverse training requirements. There is a notable difference between data management needs for structured and unstructured data, with the latter being used more widely in biomedical contexts.

Similarly, needs varied based on whether data collections systems were paper-based or primarily digital. Biomedical studies frequently employ paper-based data collection, necessitating specific guidance on storage, backup, disposal, and digitisation procedures.

This uncovered specific training implications, such as digitisation workflows, physical data storage practices, and additional confidentiality concerns. Moreover, some biomedical studies highlighted complex consent frameworks and more stringent ethical review processes, particularly around data sharing and linkage, which may not be as prominent in social science studies.

Additionally, the project identified a specific need for training in techniques related to linking cohort data with external data sources, including careful consideration of ethical implications such as consent requirements for linkage procedures.

c. Data management practices

The assessment revealed that Longitudinal Population Studies (LPS) employ a range of different data management practices. Some studies utilise bespoke, resource-intensive data management systems, creating a need for specific guidance on either transitioning to off-the-shelf solutions or optimizing the use of existing systems. Once this variety of data management systems was more fully understood, it was possible to develop recommendations for improving internal data management practices leading to better data sharing.

d. Skill levels and training needs

A tiered training approach to accommodate varying skill levels within the LPS community was identified. At a basic level, foundational skills such as file management and data cleaning were identified. However, a clear need was also identified for specialised training in advanced topics including data linkage, metadata management, and disclosure risk assessment.

e. Training preferences

Online workshops emerged as the most preferred format for LPS staff, although some expressed a preference for face-to-face workshops. The project plans incorporated interactive elements during workshops to enhance engagement.

f. Specific data management areas

The project identified several specific areas requiring enhanced training support. These included comprehensive coverage of data cleaning and preparation methodologies, metadata creation and management processes, data linkage procedures, file management systems with particular emphasis on versioning, data licensing and sharing agreement protocols, storage and backup strategies (especially for very large files), and ethical and legal concerns such as disclosure risk assessment and anonymisation techniques.

g. Harmonisation and interoperability

While existing materials adequately address the FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) principles, the assessment identified a significant gap in resources supporting data depositors in ensuring interoperability and harmonisation, especially for data intended for international research use.

While there are existing standards within specific domains and countries, no single, universally adopted standard exists that supports interdisciplinary and international interoperability. This makes it challenging to develop guidelines that are truly comprehensive and widely applicable.

Nevertheless, advancements in tools, such as those developed within initiatives like Harmony, demonstrate how technical solutions can still support harmonisation efforts across diverse environments.

3. Activity overview

The project focused on developing comprehensive training resources and workshops. Topics covered included data cleaning, management, sharing, documentation, and metadata. They conducted a series of workshops that reached over 300 participants from the UK and beyond.

The project's outputs included a suite of training materials and 'train the trainer' resources made available under a Creative Commons license, all accessible through the UKDS and CLOSER websites. For an examination of the effectiveness of producing 'train the trainer' resources, please read [Appendix 2](#).

Additionally, the team disseminated their findings through conference presentations and established promising future collaborations with a range of organisations to support ongoing training and data sharing initiatives.

Further details of project activity can be found in [Appendix 1](#).

4. Lessons learnt

a. The need for flexibility

The project team were flexible in adapting to emerging needs and challenges. The timeline was modified to build and manage relationships and to ensure comprehensive representation across the community. The stakeholder workshop format was revised to a more focused, shorter session to enhance participation rates. The project team maintained a strong commitment to inclusive training approaches, including interactive elements and different delivery styles to accommodate different learning preferences.

b. The broader landscape

The project highlighted both the critical importance of data sharing and the significant challenges faced by practitioners. As described above, specific gaps were identified, such as the lack of metadata training focused on relational databases. The project also underscored the need for training materials that bridge both social and biomedical sciences, including considerations for different data collection methods and data types.

c. What staff involved in the project learnt

Project staff gained valuable experience in developing training materials and delivering them to diverse audiences, while building expertise in effective stakeholder collaboration. The team developed an in-depth understanding of the LPS community's needs and challenges and developed skills in adapting training based on feedback and evolving requirements.

This learning will be embedded within the ongoing work of the UKDS, which plays a central role in the acquisition, curation, and dissemination of social science data in the UK and beyond, supporting over 50,000 users across research, policy, and education.

The project team expects that insights and approaches developed through this project, particularly around co-designed, responsive training, will directly inform UKDS' broader efforts to enhance data management and sharing practices as well as standard training delivery.

d. Planning for impact evidence gathering

While there is some evidence of the impact of the project, future similar projects could benefit from a more detailed plan for gathering evidence of impact. In future projects of this nature, there could be plans for collecting more short-term evidence from participants about changes in their practice and attitudes, alongside longer-term evidence of changes in, for instance, data management practices.

While information on participants (e.g. institution, national vs international, job title) was gathered, it was not processed in a consistent way, meaning the project team had incomplete information to be able to assess the reach of their work. The project team learnt that more precisely clarifying during the planning phase what information on participants they would need to collect and analyse would be an advantage.

5. Impact

Given the nature of the product and its potential longevity, impact may take a longer period to be revealed. Some suggestions for impact evidence gathering are included in section 6i.

There is evidence of excellent reach of this project.

During the period 4 June to 29 November when the workshops were held, 311 participants took part. These workshops reached international participants in Australia, Brazil, Finland, France, Italy, Netherlands, Germany, New Zealand, Nigeria, Norway, Spain, Taiwan.

Participant feedback was overwhelmingly positive, with attendees consistently finding the training sessions both interesting and practically valuable for their professional or academic work. The high recommendation rate from participants reflected the overall quality and impact of the sessions. Quotes within this section are from participant feedback.

“This is a concise training that is exactly what I needed for my role”

Through collaboration with subject matter experts, the project has addressed identified challenges and barriers to wider data access. This has included increasing awareness of specialized tools such as the [Harmony Data Tool](#) for data harmonization purposes.

“The knowledge gained today about synthetic data will significantly enhance my research. By applying synthetic data techniques, I can improve data management and ensure privacy.”

All training materials have been made freely available online under Creative Commons licensing, ensuring their long-term preservation and accessibility. The project not only facilitated the release of resources but prompted the creation of the PRUK Zenodo community, which we supported PRUK to create.

This release was also publicised in a [UK Data Service news article](#) on 28 Jan 2025. By 13 March, the training materials had been downloaded 461 times ([see Appendix 2](#)).

“It will be an excellent resource to refer back to.”

The development of a ‘train the trainer’ package enhanced the sustainability of the training program. By 13 March, the ‘train the trainer’ package has been downloaded 260 times,

suggesting enthusiasm for using these resources ([see Appendix 2](#) for elaboration of the effectiveness of this approach)..

“I’ll be able to cascade it to colleagues/academics and potentially start putting together data management sessions to deliver in-house.”

For both the training materials and the ‘train the trainer’ materials, no login is needed to access the resources on Zenodo. Consequently, it is not possible to gain a more nuanced view of reach and type of user. However, these figures tell a positive story of engagement.

There was feedback from participants that their approach to standardised data management procedures has improved.

“Version control and documentation is something I am trying to establish in my team, and I will recommend everyone attends this.”

“I got a better understanding of data linkage, particularly ethical and legal issues and [on areas such as] data management and document naming”

“I have a better awareness of best practices for metadata and for proactive planning for data sharing at the start of projects.”

As a result of the project, a new working relationship has been developed with [ATLAS](#) which may not have happened otherwise. ATLAS is a team of researchers, charities and lived experience experts funded by the Wellcome Trust. The team systematically identifies and records information about longitudinal datasets from around the world and share this information on the Atlas.

The project team became aware of ATLAS through the investment management meetings for the project, which were part of the broader coordination efforts supported by the Population Research UK initiative via ESRC.

This connection has opened up promising opportunities for sharing training materials and aligning efforts around cohort discoverability and metadata standards. The project’s focus on dissemination and stakeholder engagement created a clear rationale for the relationship and has laid the foundation for future collaboration.

6. Recommendations for future activity

a. Expanding training content

The project team has identified several key areas where training content should be expanded to meet evolving community needs. Priority should be given to developing additional training modules focusing on core competencies such as

- data cleaning
- management and sharing
- comprehensive documentation, and
- metadata provision.

There is a clear need in ensuring interoperability and harmonisation aligns with the priority areas of data management, sharing, and metadata provision. Additionally, more detailed guidance is recommended for paper-based data storage, backup, disposal, and digitisation, which supports these areas but also addresses broader data preservation needs.

Further development is needed in the area of cohort data linkage to external data sources, incorporating ethical considerations and consent requirements for linkage processes. The team suggests creating specialised training materials for handling unstructured data, such as GP records, working in collaboration with experienced LPS managers to identify and document best practices.

Additional guidance could be developed for probabilistic linking opportunities, along with in-depth study guides for newly integrated datasets or those generating significant queries.

Advanced topic areas and emerging needs within the community potentially requiring attention include machine learning applications, synthetic data generation and management, and the implementation of flexible data dictionaries.

b. Ongoing development of existing content

The approach to training delivery should continue to evolve and improve. Interactive workshops should remain a cornerstone of the program, incorporating effective elements such as breakout rooms, polls and other engaging tools.

UKDS has long run core training sessions, including LPS dedicated training but not in data management. The aim would be to run this training once a year going forward.

However, a key marker of both the success and legacy of this project is making the materials available online under Creative Commons licences to encourage others to reuse and adapt as

needed. The project team strongly believes that improving skills and capacity within the LPS community will most benefit from the ongoing availability of the training materials.

Consequently, training materials should undergo continuous refinement based on participant feedback, ensuring relevance and effectiveness. Particular attention should be paid to ensuring training provisions are inclusive and support diversity in all aspects.

c. Further dissemination of training materials

There are successful links to the Zenodo materials from the [UKDS](#) and [CLOSER](#) websites. A future aim should be to ensure signposting of the materials from as many LPS and training communities as possible, such as UKLLC and NCRM. Ideally, the materials will also be signposted from the PRUK hub.

d. Focus on specific data types and formats

Special attention should be given to developing training that further addresses the unique challenges of managing biomedical data, particularly the complexities associated with different data types, such as those derived from blood sample.

While the anonymisation training session already emphasises the careful handling of biomedical data, including data derived from blood, urine, and other medical sources, there is a need to establish clearer parameters for these data types. For instance, in longitudinal studies, predefined thresholds for acceptable variations between waves or sweeps should be set, including guidance on when to apply top or bottom coding to ensure disclosure risk is properly mitigated.

To further support this, the team also recommends expanding training and guidance with particular emphasis on version control and file management practices to ensure that data integrity is preserved over time.

e. Resource development and sharing

Future resource development should prioritise accessibility and long-term preservation. All training materials should continue to be made available online under a Creative Commons license, ensuring long-term preservation, discoverability, and maximum impact.

It would be beneficial to make a comprehensive library of materials available on the PRUK hub, once this can be technically set up and supported.

f. Further developing collaboration and engagement

Maintaining and expanding collaborative relationships will be a key factor in continuing the success of this project. The team recommends continuing close collaboration with LPS representatives and key stakeholders to identify emerging gaps and potential solutions. The project should actively engage with data providers in creating and sharing best practice.

The team suggests facilitating additional sessions, recognizing that many LPS organisations prefer online delivery formats. Better involvement with existing networks, such as CLOSER, will be beneficial for both avoiding duplication of effort and for expanding reach and impact.

Exploring approaches to deepening existing collaborations and partnerships (for example with Harmony and UKLLC) could be investigated.

With the project team having created a new working relationship with [ATLAS](#), there is potential to develop this relationship further. They currently make their metadata records available in [Dublin Core](#) but are keen to work with the UK Data Service to see if using DDI would be possible. This avenue should be explored further.

g. Exploring further opportunities for promotion

The team could actively pursue opportunities for presenting at conferences such as IASSIST and ESRA. Publication possibilities in journals could also be explored.

h. Post training programme evaluation and evidence gathering

The project team believes that through the implementation of skills development training, the quality assurance processes for survey data have been enhanced. However, follow up with select participants through a survey, focus group or other evaluative process would provide stronger evidence for this.

In addition, the project team discovered that participant information was not processed and presented to them in a consistent manner, making analysis of job roles, location etc difficult. Future projects should work towards more consistent data processing and analysis to help understand reach of the project.

i. Gathering further evidence of impact of the project

The project team believes that their efforts have resulted in more consistently prepared data deposits at the UKDS and other repositories, ensuring better long-term curation and preservation. Over time, evidence could be gathered on the quality of preparation of data deposits to back up this belief. Impact could be assessed through, for example, assessing whether there have been more questions about anonymisation or data formats from potential new depositors or whether the UKDS collections team have had had approaches from new data depositors.

The project team believe the project has enhanced the capabilities of participants through widening understanding of standardised data management procedures, thereby expanding the pool of expertise available to support wider data sharing initiatives. Over time, evidence of this can be gathered to support this supposition. Evidence could include the extent to which sharing practices are standardised across responsible repositories and TREs nationally and

internationally. The Forums [SDAP](#) (nationally) and [ISDFPN](#) (internationally) can actively support that process via knowledge exchange events.

Understanding the impact of a project of this nature needs a longer-term view, gathering evidence over a longer period to demonstrate changed attitudes, behaviours and adoption of best practice. Some examples of evidence that could be gathered are included above – others may appear over time.

Appendix 1: Key activities and outputs

a. Key activities

Initially, the team conducted an internal audit of existing training materials and resources to identify gaps and areas requiring improvement. This was complemented by an external audit of training provision, conducted through a survey and stakeholder workshop. The team worked closely with LPS representatives and key stakeholders to identify unmet needs and co-design appropriate training solutions.

The development phase focused on creating training resources covering essential topics such as data cleaning, management, sharing, documentation, and metadata. This included the creation of comprehensive training materials encompassing guidance documents, notes, slides, training datasets, and feedback forms.

The delivery phase involved conducting workshops in various formats, including online interactive sessions, pilot workshops, and ‘train the trainer’ sessions. Throughout the process, the team gathered and incorporated feedback to refine and adapt materials. They also maintained thorough documentation of the project process and developed a dedicated project webpage for disseminating information and outputs.

b. Outputs

Workshops

The project delivered a comprehensive workshop program that included introductory training sessions covering foundational research data management concepts, ethical and legal considerations, data organisation, documentation, anonymisation, and data sharing.

Specialised sessions focused on advanced topics such as synthetic data and data harmonisation. The team conducted a pilot workshop to gather initial feedback and refine training materials, as well as a stakeholder workshop to identify training gaps and collaboration opportunities.

Specific workshops were tailored for data managers and professionals working in Trusted Research Environments (TREs).

Attendance at workshops

Enhancing longitudinal data sharing – Day 1	94
Enhancing longitudinal data sharing – Day 2	74
Introduction to synthetic data for longitudinal data managers	81
Transforming data management with the Harmony Data Tool: A hands-on introduction	62
Total	311

These workshops reached international participants in countries including Australia, Brazil, Finland, France, Italy, Netherlands, Germany, New Zealand, Nigeria, Norway, Spain, Taiwan.

From the available data, we estimate that approximately 78% of the participants were from the UK and 22% international participants.

Training Materials

The project produced a comprehensive suite of [training materials](#) designed for reuse and adaptation. These included detailed guidance documents, notes, slides, training datasets, and feedback forms, all made available under a Creative Commons license to ensure long-term preservation and discoverability. The materials were developed with accessibility in mind, incorporating different modes of delivery to accommodate varied learning needs.

These materials are currently signposted from the [UKDS](#) and [CLOSER](#) websites.

Download totals as at 13 March:

- [PRUK UKDS: Introductory Research Data Management Course - Enhancing Longitudinal Data Sharing](#)
349 downloads
- [PRUK UKDS: Introductory Research Data Management Course - Enhancing Longitudinal Data Sharing - Recordings](#)
112 downloads

Total downloads of the training materials: 461 downloads.

'Train the Trainer' materials

To ensure sustainable impact, the project developed ['train-the-trainer' versions of all slides](#), enhancing the adaptability of the course content. These materials were specifically designed to support others in delivering the training effectively, ensuring consistent quality and approach across different delivery contexts.

[Appendix 2](#) elaborates on the effectiveness of this approach.

These materials are also currently signposted from the [UKDS](#) and [CLOSER](#) websites.

Download totals as at 13 March:

- [PRUK UKDS: Introductory Research Data Management Course - Enhancing Longitudinal Data Sharing - Train the Trainer Materials](#)
260 downloads

Making Word versions of materials available

The team has made Word versions of documents available on Zenodo, complementing existing PDF versions. The reference guides are in both Word and PDF to enhance accessibility and reusability – as described briefly in the [Zenodo metadata](#).

Making the training and 'train the trainer' materials available via a PRUK community on Zenodo

The team supported PRUK in creating a dedicated [PRUK community on Zenodo](#) to better manage project outputs.

Conference presentations and publications

The project's findings and outcomes were disseminated through presentations and posters at major conferences including SLLS, IASSIST, and ESRA. The team also identified potential opportunities for publication in the International Journal of Population Data Science, ensuring broader impact within the academic community.

Future collaborations

The project established several promising pathways for future collaboration, including partnerships with CLOSER and other key studies. Significant working relationships were developed with the UK Longitudinal Linkage Collaboration (UKLLC), and exploration of collaborative opportunities with Harmony regarding data harmonisation tools was initiated. The team also established partnerships with other organisations and projects, such as PRUK, to support future training and data sharing initiatives.

Appendix 2: The effectiveness of ‘train the trainer’ approaches

This project has taken the ‘train the trainer’ approach. This approach means that people are equipped to then spread the knowledge throughout their workplaces. This enables the knowledge to be tailored to their organisation and practices.

The effectiveness of the ‘train the trainer’ approach has been evaluated in a variety of settings. Those considering their use in social science settings highlighting their potential when well-structured and tailored to participant needs.

A study in Hong Kong assessed a two-day ‘train the trainer’ workshop aimed at equipping social service workers with to enhance family well-being through community-based interventions. Results indicated improvements in participants’ perceived knowledge, self-efficacy, attitudes, and intentions to apply the training (Lai *et al.*, 2017).

Similarly, research on capacity building in public health found that ‘train the trainer’ programs effectively disseminated evidence-based decision-making principles, leading to increased knowledge and application among professionals (Yarber *et al* 2015).

The effectiveness of ‘train the trainer’ programs is influenced by the delivery methods used. A systematic review found that blended learning—combining interactive, multifaceted approaches with supplementary materials, yielded the best results in training health and social care professionals (Pearce *et al*, 2012).

These findings collectively support the structured and varied training approach we have adopted with asynchronous materials prepared including webinar recordings and written materials.

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